

Hecate: An Intelligent Chatbot System for Customer Service Terminals

Matheus D. Rezende, Richarlyson A. D'Emery

Unidade Acadêmica de Serra Talhada (UAST), Universidade Federal Rural de Pernambuco (UFRPE)

Serra Talhada, PE, Brazil

Caixa Postal – 56903-970 – Serra Talhada – PE – Brazil

matheusdsantosr.si@gmail.com

Abstract. *Context:* Artificial Intelligence (AI) is increasingly adopted by companies, particularly through chatbots, which have become a viable solution for customer service on digital platforms, offering faster and more accessible interactions. *Objective:* This work aims to develop a chatbot for customer service in commercial establishments, focusing on improving user experience and providing more dynamic and personalized responses. *Method:* The development followed a structured approach based on requirements gathering, literature review, and full-stack implementation using Python, Django, React, and PostgreSQL. The chatbot leverages Gemini in its learning process, incorporating techniques such as synonym generation and embeddings to enhance response accuracy and contextual understanding. Additionally, the system adopts the Model-View-Controller (MVC) architectural pattern, enabling scalability, modularity, and efficient separation of concerns. *Result:* The main outcome of this research is the Hecate chatbot, which enables customer service based on data related to a commercial establishment. In controlled test scenarios, the system achieved accuracy rates above 85% in intent recognition and reduced average response time to under 2 seconds, even when handling queries with spelling errors or incomplete input. The solution replaces traditional Frequently Asked Questions (FAQ) pages with an interactive system capable of personalizing interactions, such as providing product information and company details. Furthermore, the results demonstrate the feasibility of integrating modern AI techniques into real-world applications, contributing to more efficient, scalable, and intelligent customer service systems.

Keywords: Chatbot, Customer Service, Semantic Search, Embeddings, AI

1. Introduction

Recently, there has been a significant increase in interest in the use and implementation of dialogue generation systems. Many technology companies are using virtual assistants or chat agents to meet their needs [Sojasingarayar 2020].

Generally, e-commerce customer service is provided through conversations with online customer service agents, which involves human intervention to answer questions related to product names, categories, prices, and other common characteristics [Zafar 2023]. However, studies involving AI as a discipline analyze customer service factors. Among these applications, e-commerce platforms have been inventing new ways to

communicate with customers, notably through the use of chatbots [Grewal, Roggeveen, and Nordfält 2017].

Chatbots are intelligent conversational computer programs that mimic human conversation in its natural form [Jia 2003; Sojasingarayar 2020; Bala et al. 2017]. A chatbot can process user input and generate an output [Ayanouz, Abdelhakim, and Benhmed 2020; Kumar and Ali 2020]. Typically, they receive natural language text as input, and the output should be as relevant as possible to the user's input phrase. Chatbots can also be defined as "online human-computer dialogue system(s) using natural language" [Cahn 2017].

Customer service plays a key role in an organization's ability to generate income and revenue. Generally, this area is the most resource-intensive in a company, requiring billions annually to enhance customer perception [Srivastava 2021]. It is observed that the adoption of information technologies improves the customer experience across various channels—from non-human interfaces such as vending machines and self service kiosks to websites and apps—aligning digital functionalities with users' real needs [Stickdorn 2014].

Thus, the following **research question** arises: "How can chatbots assist consumers in in-person retail environments?"

AI has been applied in sectors such as education, healthcare, entertainment, and gaming. In e-commerce, its impact is particularly significant: websites use algorithms to provide personalized responses, recall items from wish lists, and notify customers about discounts and promotions [Srivastava 2021]. As the world becomes increasingly digital, chatbots are becoming widely adopted automated service assistants in online stores. In these systems, textual interaction allows customers to respond to both the content and style of messages, improving engagement and satisfaction [Dube and Benedetto 2002].

Against a backdrop of constant advances in software and hardware, self-service solutions have become established across multiple service sectors—from payment kiosks to information kiosks—offering speed and autonomy to the end user [Meuter et al. 2000; Cunningham et al. 2008].

When it comes to designing and adopting chatbots in the consumer journey, Pantano and Pizzi (2020) note that: "retailers can choose pre-designed chatbot platforms or develop their own; from a technological standpoint, conversational agents are designed to mimic natural language."

Aiming to contribute through a technological solutions-based approach, this research has the general objective of developing a chatbot to assist with customer service in retail establishments. This solution aims to provide an environment in which a customer not only has easier access to information about products but also makes their experience in the environment more engaging. To achieve this objective, the following specific objectives are outlined: (i) identify and apply machine learning techniques; (ii) design customer service software; and (iii) develop the software.

The following sections are organized to provide a comprehensive overview of the work. In Section 2, the theoretical framework will introduce the concept of this study, highlighting AI and machine learning, as well as Gemini. In Section 3,

related works are presented. The methodology is presented in Section 4. Section 5 presents the results. Section 6 presents the conclusion and discussion of the research, as well as suggestions for future work. Finally, the references supporting this article are provided.

2. Theoretical Framework

2.1 AI and Machine Learning

AI is a branch of computer science that aims to build mechanisms, whether physical or digital, that simulate the human ability to think and make decisions. It is the study of phenomena of human intelligence and the development of computer systems capable of emulating human behavioral patterns and generating problem-solving knowledge [Min 2010]. Holding the promise of overcoming human cognitive and physical limits [Wilson et al. 2018], there is a multitude of potential applications, especially in improving organizational performance and productivity [Dwivedi et al. 2019].

As technologies have become more advanced, AI has become more user-friendly, and recently, it has become commonplace in many end-user applications, including real-time interactions with computers, known as chatbots [Adamopoulou and Moussiades 2020].

In today's world, companies are coming up with new ways to communicate with potential customers using chatbots, automated feedback forms, and more. AI helps them find the right customers; similarly, e-commerce businesses are reaping benefits from this technology, where customers also enjoy a better experience and greater satisfaction through AI-driven e-commerce portals featuring visual intelligence search, voice search, and improved after-sales services, among other features [Srivastava 2021].

Another factor contributing to improved user experience is the scalability of chatbots, as they can handle multiple users simultaneously, providing faster responses and an enhanced user experience [Adamopoulou and Moussiades 2023].

Furthermore, the integration of different chatbots, such as the Alexa-Cortana integration, enables communication between agents and can contribute to a better user experience and customer satisfaction. Intrapersonal chatbots, such as the Messenger and WhatsApp chat apps, improve the user experience by acting as companions and understanding users as humans [Adamopoulou and Moussiades 2023]. Similarly, intrapersonal chatbots that offer services such as restaurant reservations and flight bookings can provide a better user experience and customer satisfaction [Adamopoulou and Moussiades 2023; Aslam 2023]. Typically, product information is provided or the product is sold through a conversation with online customer service agents, which involves human intervention to answer questions related to the product name, category, price, and other common characteristics [Zafar 2023].

The conversational capabilities of traditional chatbots are inflexible; that is, they can respond to the user only if there is a (lexical) match between the user's query and the set of questions and answers stored in their knowledge base [Abbate, Thiel, and Kamps 2005].

Research seeks to elucidate the extent to which the implicit style in a chatbot's communication can affect customer perception in the context of online shopping. This topic is recent and has gained increased academic attention [Li and Wang 2023]. For example, Roy and Naidoo (2021) suggested that chatbots should adapt their communication style to the customer's profile. For consumers with a present-focused mindset, a friendlier and more informal tone tends to be more effective. For those who plan their decisions based on future expectations, however, a more technical and competent style can generate greater trust, increasing both purchase intent and positive brand perception.

2.2. Machine Learning

The concept of Machine Learning (ML) is not new; however, in recent years, these technologies have been revolutionized by the availability of big data and advances in computing power. ML has become increasingly popular across various sectors, including healthcare, finance, retail, and more [Sharifani and Amini 2023].

The rapid advancement of generative AI models is revolutionizing various fields, including education, industry, and business. Tech giants like Google have introduced their model, called Gemini [Kalluri and Kokala 2024]. Gemini uses pre-trained ML models to uncover the intent behind what the user says. These models, trained on a large volume of text and code, can label users with high accuracy. This means that Gemini's ML model can effectively categorize these points by analyzing the input based on its vast internal database, leading to a personalized and informative response [AlGhozali and Mukminatun 2024].

ML is the study of computer algorithms that give computers the ability to automatically learn from data and past experiences to identify patterns and make predictions without human involvement. ML and its applications in various fields of study are considered a component of AI [Mahesh 2020; Carleo et al. 2019; Joshi 2020]. It is a rapidly developing field that has seen widespread adoption in recent years. It involves the use of learning algorithms based on data, aiming to improve the accuracy and efficiency of predictions and decisions. ML typically involves the use of statistical methods to learn from data [Sharifani and Amini 2023].

ML can be of four types (Figure 1): supervised learning, weakly supervised learning (WSL), unsupervised learning, and reinforcement learning.

Figure 1. Taxonomy of machine learning. Source: [Ren, Wang, and Zhang 2023]

Supervised learning has been widely used and has achieved greater success compared to other approaches. Formally, this method learns a function that maps training examples to outputs. Each training data point contains a feature vector that describes the object and a label representing the expected correct value. There are two main types of supervised learning tasks: classification and regression. In classification, the label indicates the category of the example, while in regression it represents a numerical output value [Ren, Wang, and Zhang 2023].

In contrast, unsupervised learning directly improves the information in the data without ground truth labels and seeks to represent an understanding of the data to generate outputs. There are five main approaches in unsupervised learning: self-supervised learning, clustering, density estimation, dimensionality reduction, and association rules [Hastie, Tibshirani, and Friedman 2009; IBM 2020].

Weak learning can be viewed as a type of supervised learning; however, the data is labeled incompletely or with noise to produce models with moderate accuracy [Cechin 2023]. There are three types of weak learning based on label confidence: incomplete, imprecise, and inaccurate supervision. For incomplete supervision, most training examples lack labels, and the remaining ones use ground-truth labels [Ren, Wang, and Zhang 2023]. The second type, imprecise supervision, occurs when training examples have only coarse-grained labels. This means that the supervised information is provided, but not with the expected level of detail [Minaee et al. 2021]. On the other hand, imprecise supervision refers to scenarios in which the labels of the training data are not always correct, indicating the possibility that some labels contain errors [Minaee et al. 2021].

Meanwhile, reinforcement learning (RL) is a learning approach in which an AI agent interacts with its surrounding environment through trial and error and learns an

optimal behavioral strategy based on reward signals received from previous interactions. This RL agent's learning process mimics the human/animal learning approach. Recent years have highlighted its adaptability to other scientific and engineering fields, emerging as an efficient technique for solving complex sequential decision-making tasks. This learning offers an opportunity in technology where system models are unavailable or are too difficult and/or too expensive to build [Shakya, Pillai, and Chakrabarty 2023].

2.3. Gemini

The development of large language models (LLMs) by OpenAI, such as GPT-3, has paved the way for significant growth in chatbots, such as ChatGPT-3.5. Currently, multimodal AI tools, such as ChatGPT-4 or ChatGPT-4V, and language models can interact with and identify various inputs interspersed with a variety of texts, images, audio, videos, and documents. Inworld AI, Meta ImageBind, Runway Gen-2, and Google Gemini are the most widely used [Imran and Almusharraf 2024].

Gemini is Google's most advanced and capable GenAI tool, offering a wide range of features that set it apart in the AI landscape, as it boasts more robust capabilities across all modalities, as well as state-of-the-art understanding and reasoning performance in each domain [Team et al. 2023].

Using the Google AI Python SDK is the easiest way for Python developers to create solutions using Gemini Application Programming Interfaces (APIs). This API provides access to the various models available in Gemini, such as the 1.5 Flash, 1.5 Flash-8B, and 1.5 Pro models. Gemini models are built from the ground up to be multimodal, so they can reason seamlessly using text, images, and code [Team et al. 2023].

One of Gemini's functions lies in its use of an embedding generation model for words, phrases, and sentences. The resulting embeddings can be used for tasks such as semantic search, text classification, clustering, and many others [Lee et al. 2024].

The concept of embedding emerged as dense vector representations of words or phrases, with the ability to map syntactic and semantic relationships in a vector space, which is essential for Natural Language Processing (NLP) applications [Almeida and Xexéo 2019; Camacho-Collados and Pilehvar 2022].

One of the greatest advances in word embedding technology emerged in 2013, when a Google team led by Tomas Mikolov created Word2Vec [Mikolov et al. 2013a; Mikolov et al. 2013b]. A word embedding solution that uses deep learning (unsupervised) techniques to capture word associations from a large text corpus, leveraging both the (continuous) set of words and "skip-gram" approaches to define the context of words (semantics), that is, from a central word, neighboring words can be predicted, thereby grouping multiple words based on a single input word [Worth 2023].

Word embeddings are classified into two types: count-based and prediction-based. In the case of count-based embeddings, the representation is derived from word counts and word frequencies, while prediction-based embeddings are derived from the context of words (words neighboring a central word). These form the basis of the state-of-the-art approach in neural language models [Adamuthe 2020]. The most commonly used embeddings are those from the prediction-based family [Gutiérrez and

Keith 2019]. For this research, the Gemini Embedding library is used to create embeddings in production, which is an unsupervised approach since the model automatically generates the embeddings based on the input data. Using this approach, it is possible to measure the distance between words/vectors within a context, given that the embedding contains the contextual information from the data used to construct it.

Based on the Gemini models, it becomes possible to use various methods and functions, one of which is `embed_content`, responsible for generating a text embedding vector from the input content using `Content`, a specific model from Gemini Embedding. In this research, we use **text-embedding-004**, the latest update released by Google. These text embeddings are used to measure the relationship between strings and are widely used in many AI applications. Figure 2 illustrates the code for using the `embed_content` function.

```
import google.generativeai as genai

# Configurando a API do Gemini
GOOGLE_API_KEY = SECRET_KEY
genai.configure(api_key=GOOGLE_API_KEY)

# Nome do modelo
embed_model = 'models/text-embedding-004'

# Geração do embedding
genai.embed_content(model=embed_model,
                    content='texto',
                    task_type="RETRIEVAL_DOCUMENT")["embedding"]
```

Figure 2. Sample code for generating embeddings.

Another function is `generate_content`, which is responsible for generating content and main outputs. It is a multifunctional function for generating responses from a selected model. Table 1 lists the available arguments for this function.

Tabela 1. Available arguments for the generate_content function.

Arguments	
model_name	The name of the model to query.
safety_settings	Default safe filter configuration. This controls which content is blocked by the API before being returned.
generation_config	Model settings. The <code>genai.GenerationConfig</code> library configuration sets this argument to the used.

`generation_config` allows for complex model configurations. Some parameters that can be modified are: `candidateCount`, which specifies the number of generated responses to be returned (currently only configurable to a specific value); `maxOutputTokens`, which defines the maximum number of tokens to be included in a candidate; and `temperature`, which controls the randomness of the output. For temperature, values from 0.0 to 2.0 can be used, where higher values are used to obtain

more creative responses and lower values to obtain more objective and predictable responses [Loeber 2024].

3. Related Work

This section presents research highlighting various solutions in the context of improving hardware and software, addressing the central theme of this study. Additionally, it explores a technological perspective that uses AI as a driving force for innovative solutions.

In the study conducted by Cui et al. (2017), titled "**SuperAgent: A Customer Service Chatbot for E-commerce Websites**", software was developed—specifically a web browser extension—to provide a chatbot named SuperAgent, designed for e-commerce sites to answer repetitive and simple questions, as well as to enhance business operations by offering 24-hour customer service.

This extension performs web searches and scraping to collect data directly from product pages. Figure 3 shows how, based on this knowledge base, the chatbot interacts to provide product information, answer customer questions, and display related reviews.

SuperAgent uses predefined responses that adapt to the user's question. If there is no suitable response, the system sends an automatic message and forwards the request to a human agent.

SuperAgent integrates various third-party models, refined and trained with data collected from web pages by the extension. Figure 4 illustrates the system flow: first, data is collected and stored in the database, where it is organized; next, the data is analyzed, embeddings are generated, similarity is calculated, and a comparison is made with the input (user's question).

Figure 3 SuperAgent—an example of an extension interacting with the Amazon website, including product information, customer questions and answers, as well as reviews.

Source: [Cui et al. 2017]. Source: [Cui et al. 2017]

Figure 4. Overview of the SuperAgent system. Source [Cui et al. 2017]

The extension uses search and web scraping techniques to extract information from web pages and store it in a database, allowing it to be organized in a structured manner. This data is then sent to the processing “engine,” which employs the Deep Structured Semantic Model (DSSM) [Huang et al. 2013] to compare the user’s input with the information available in the database. Only records whose score reaches a predefined threshold are selected and ranked, and their responses are generated from preconfigured models.

In parallel, the system uses a regression forest [Meinshausen and Ridgeway 2006] trained on the same dataset. This model handles more specific question matching: given a question q already mapped in the database (for example, “Does this model come with a keyboard?”) and the user’s question q' (“Does the product have a keyboard?”), the regression forest evaluates the similarity between them. To 13 enrich this process, we also employ GloVe embeddings [Pennington et al. 2014] and word-pair comparisons using PairingWords [Han et al. 2013].

When the user’s input is deemed irrelevant (such as greetings, as shown in Figure 5), the system activates a chit-chat model trained on over five million question-answer pairs extracted from Twitter. This model focuses on short interactions (up to fifteen words), covering common greetings and responses to keep the dialogue more natural

Q: hello
R: hey how are you?
Q: thank you
R: you’re very welcome sir
Q: you are so cute
R: u r more

Figure 5. Example of output from this model. Source: [Cui et al. 2017]

In the paper titled "**Development of an E-Commerce Chatbot for a University Shopping Mall**", Oguntosin and Olomo (2021) present a chatbot called Hebron. Hebron was developed to make daily life easier for members of the Covenant University Community, who faced the inconvenience of traveling long distances to a shopping mall

to find desired products. With this in mind, the system offers: (i) real-time conversation; (ii) product information, such as price and availability; (iii) the ability to make payments directly through the chatbot.

Figure 6 shows Hebron’s main interface. On the backend, Hebron is implemented in Python, while the frontend uses React. Among the libraries employed, SpaCy stands out, responsible for generating embeddings and performing lemmatization—that is, converting words to their base form, as defined in Pant, Sharma, and Kundu (2024)—as well as providing tokenization and linguistic annotation features that identify the part of speech of each token.

For natural language processing, Hebron relies on the Recast.ai API. This platform handles the creation, training, and monitoring of conversations and provides a webhook that allows the chatbot to be integrated into the web interface. When the user sends a message, the algorithm compares the input with the “intents” stored in Hebron—a repository of phrases or expressions with equivalent meanings—to determine the most appropriate response.

The Hebron database stores both training data (a set of e-commerce information) and past conversations. As shown in Figure 7, this information is continuously entered into and queried by the system, allowing the knowledge base to be improved and the quality of responses to be refined over time.

Figure 6. Hebron chatbot. Source: [Oguntosin e Olomo 2021]

Figure 7. Hebron activity diagram for inquiries. Source: [Oguntosin e Olomo 2021]

In the paper titled “**Implementation of a Web-Based Chatbot Using Machine Learning for Question and Answer Services in Universities**”, Dewantara and Aryanto (2024) present a chatbot for a university website, primarily responsible for answering questions related to the institution.

They report having faced some initial difficulties: creating a chatbot using only the student enrollment data available on the Universitas Teknologi Yogyakarta websites and converting the data, which was initially in .doc format, to JSON.

The main programming language used was Python to code the ML algorithm with a neural network, combined with HTML, CSS, and JavaScript to integrate the ML into the website, in addition to various Python libraries, such as Sastrawi, Flask, and NumPy. The methodology used in this research is divided into six stages, presented in Figure 8.

Figure 8. Research methodology. Source: [Dewantara e Aryanto 2024]

In the problem identification stage, an analysis of the university’s system is conducted, with a special focus on the accuracy and efficiency of the responses provided to students and their families. The process occurs in two ways: the user navigates through options available on the institution’s website or fills out a form with questions that are forwarded to a website administrator, who returns the response after some time.

Once this inefficiency in service was identified, the idea arose to offer a chatbot capable of providing instant responses.

During the data collection phase, both information extracted from the university's websites and data obtained through interviews with students—conducted via questionnaires—are utilized. Both contain questions relevant to the chatbot's operation. Next, the system design is developed, represented by an activity diagram that models the chatbot's operational flow.

The activity flow, shown in Figure 9, receives a question asked by the user as input. Initially, this question is processed using the ML model, which checks whether it matches one of the intents already trained based on the available data. If the intent is not recognized, a standard message is displayed to the user; otherwise, the question is processed, and the appropriate response is determined. Before displaying this response, it is evaluated to see if it satisfactorily addresses the input. If the evaluation is positive, the message is displayed to the user; otherwise, the response is reprocessed until a satisfactory level of quality is achieved.

During the system implementation phase, the chatbot is coded and integrated into the university's website. This phase was divided into five stages:

1. **Preprocessing:** the system selects data from each document (.doc) and performs three steps: tokenization, filtering, and lemmatization.
2. **Data transformation into JSON:** this allows the system to identify question patterns and associate each pattern with its respective answer. To do this, each word is broken down into elements that facilitate mapping.
3. **Training:** the collected data is used to train the model, aiming to achieve a satisfactory level of accuracy.
4. **Construction of the “bag of words” model:** a set of words (text) is represented in the form of binary vectors, where each position indicates the presence or absence of a specific term. 5. **Full connection:** the resulting binary vector is fed into the input layer of the neural network, signaling the hidden layer to process the information appropriately.

Figure 9. Activity Diagram. Source: [Dewantara e Aryanto 2024]

In the testing phase, the chatbot's performance is evaluated using a confusion matrix, calculating the accuracy, precision, and recall rates. Finally, in the conclusion phase, the chatbot is made available on the university's website, ready to answer user questions using ML. Figures 10 and 11 show examples of the chatbot in use.

Figure 10. Modal do Chatbot. Source: [Dewantara e Aryanto 2024]

Figure 11. Message tests on the chatbot: (a) regarding the campus address; (b) regarding the campus address with dialogue input errors; and (c) untrained input. Source: [Dewantara e Aryanto 2024].

Figure 10 illustrates the chatbot window on the university’s website. Figure 11 shows dialogue tests with the system. For example, Figure 11(a) demonstrates the system’s effectiveness in responding to inquiries about the campus address, even when the question is phrased differently. In Figure 11(b), it can be seen that, even with several incorrectly typed words, the chatbot manages to provide satisfactory answers. In Figure 11(c), however, when no pattern is identified in the user’s question, the chatbot automatically returns the message, “I didn’t understand.”

3.1. Comparative Study

Table 2 presents a comparison between related studies and this research, highlighting strengths and weaknesses, as well as the characteristics of each solution.

Table 2. Comparative Analysis of Related Studies

Characteristic	[Cui et al. 2017]	[Oguntosin and Olomo 2021]	[Dewantara and Aryanto 2024]	This Study
Intended for retail	Yes	Yes	No	Yes
Real-time conversation	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
Environment for entering new data into the knowledge base	No	No	No	Yes
Conversation history	No	No	No	Yes
Technology	AI models, WordNet, and two neural network methodologies	React and Python	Python, HTML, CSS, and JavaScript	Python, React, CSS, Tailwind CSS, Sklearn, and Gemini

The selected features were defined based on essential criteria for the development of commerce-oriented chatbots. The "commerce-oriented" criterion allowed us to compare this research with other solutions applied to this segment. "Real-time conversation" represents the basic requirement for immediate interaction with the user. The ability to "adapt to the user" is highlighted as one of Hecate's key differentiators, as it provides a personalized experience. Furthermore, the implementation of an environment for adding new data to the knowledge base and the functionality to store conversation history are fundamental for maintaining a dynamic and contextualized dialogue, surpassing static FAQ approaches.

This research is similar to that of Oguntosin and Olomo (2021), as both focus on product-related inquiries. On the other hand, the solution by Cui et al. (2017) has a broader scope in commerce in general, unlike the work by Oguntosin and Olomo (2021), which was developed specifically for a university shopping mall.

Unlike other studies, Cui et al. (2017) integrated their work with other AI models, an innovative approach according to the literature review. In fact, SuperAgent is cited in several articles, indicating the use of this method. This study adopts a distinct approach by incorporating third-party technology; that is, no neural networks, embeddings, or custom libraries are created for training; instead, off-the-shelf models are used to handle this process.

In the work by Oguntosin and Olomo (2021), featuring the chatbot known as Hebron, a high learning capacity for new products is observed, allowing a shopping mall administrator to add items and their information, and the chatbot to learn from this data, creating an embedding of the user's input to compare it with Hebron's database.

In the study by Dewantara and Aryanto (2024), the creation of a neural network capable of processing texts subjected to filtering and tokenization stands out, transforming them into binary vectors to feed the network's learning. As in Oguntosi and Olomo (2021), there is a data training process to achieve a satisfactory level of accuracy.

4. Method

This section presents the methodological steps for conducting this research.

4.1. Literature Review

To develop the solution, it is necessary to gather information to achieve the main objective of the research: to provide quick and useful feedback on the products and/or services of a commercial establishment. However, to do so, the system must learn from both input data and data stored in the database. The exploratory phase is crucial for precisely defining the study's scope and identifying the data sources.

The identification of works in the literature related to the topic of this research is current and constantly updated. For this purpose, the Google Scholar search engine was used with the following search string: (“chatbot” OR “artificial intelligence” OR “deep learning”) AND (“e-commerce” OR “market” OR “business” OR “university”) AND (“conversation” OR “analysis”) AND (“program” OR “software”). The keywords were also translated into English to expand the results obtained in that language.

The following exclusion criteria were used to select the studies: (i) articles not written in English or Portuguese; (ii) studies unrelated to AI or chatbots; (iii) duplicate studies; and (iv) articles not available for free access. The inclusion criteria are: (i) scientific articles related to chatbots that foster discussion on their development; (ii) studies that apply AI techniques to improve processes or activities; and (iii) those that make people's lives easier in commercial applications.

The first 50 papers obtained in the search are analyzed, and if the results prove insufficient, the snowballing technique is applied to identify new references based on those papers.

4.2. Software Development

The software development follows the architecture shown in Figure 12.

After the user interacts with the interface, the entered text is sent to the backend via an API. The system performs initial checks to confirm receipt of the message and first verifies whether the message was actually received, free of transmission errors (e.g., complete absence of content or connection errors); in case of errors, processing is interrupted. Otherwise, even if the text is incomplete or contains typos, the message proceeds normally to the next stages of the chatbot.

Next, the text undergoes grammatical analysis and correction using Gemini, which corrects obvious errors (for example, converting “Do you hav orei cooki” to “Do you have oreo cookies?”) and standardizes accents and punctuation. After adjustment,

Gemini compares the entry to the database using parameters such as brand, quantity format, and product descriptors. 20 If it identifies “Oreo” as a brand, for example, it performs a targeted search for corresponding products.

Figure 12. System architecture.

The chatbot’s learning process is continuous: during the session, user instructions—such as “I want to see only products from this brand”—update the context and restrict future queries to the specified brand, keeping this filter active until the user modifies it or ends the conversation.

In the administrative interface, the employee fills out a product registration form on the frontend, which triggers a request to the backend. The system automatically validates whether all fields have been filled out correctly. If there are inconsistencies, it returns error messages so the employee can correct the form. Once all data is validated, the product registration is completed, automatically generating or incrementing synonyms (if the field is not filled in manually), thereby ensuring the continuous updating of the knowledge base. Finally, the employee receives confirmation feedback indicating that the registration was successful.

For the frontend, React is used as the primary language, also responsible for communication with the backend via JavaScript Object Notation (JSON) through the Django REST Framework, a Python library for building APIs that adopts the Model View-Controller (MVC) architectural pattern. This pattern allows the presentation, logic, and data layers to be developed independently, facilitating maintenance and extensions: changes to the layout do not interfere with data manipulation, and vice versa.

In Django, Models are Python classes mapped to database tables. Views are functions or classes that receive HTTP requests and return responses according to the system’s logic. REST (Representational State Transfer) defines an architectural style for creating web services and promoting interoperability between the client and server. The REST-based API decouples the client (front-end) from the server (back-end), simplifying data management and avoiding duplication of database access logic.

For the system's visual style, Tailwind CSS is used in conjunction with custom CSS rules. On the backend, Django also manages CRUD (create, read, update, and delete) operations for products in the system.

A key feature of Hecate lies in the chatbot's continuous learning. During the product registration phase, synonyms are automatically generated for each item using the GenerativeAI library, which utilizes the Gemini model—an advanced AI developed by Google capable of processing and reasoning about various types of data (text, images, audio, and video) to construct general and contextualized representations [Team et al. 2023]. These synonyms enrich the knowledge base, allowing the chatbot to recognize variations in the terms used by users and provide increasingly accurate responses.

Embeddings are also generated using the **genai.embed_content** function from Gemini Embedding, via the **text-embedding-004** model (as described in Section 2).

To generate responses and other outputs, the `generate_content` function is used, which in this research employs the `gemini-2.0-flash` model—the latest version recommended by Google. This is a multifunctional function responsible for producing content based on the selected model.

Through the **generation_config** argument of this function, a more detailed configuration of the model is performed. For example, `temperature = 0.5` is set to obtain more deterministic responses. To make the interaction more dynamic, the `start_chat` function is used, which manages multiple rounds of dialogue and allows the user to gradually progress toward solving complex or multi-part problems.

The Database Management System (DBMS) used is PostgreSQL, where all interactions with the system are stored. To measure the similarity between the user's prompt and possible records (such as products, brands, or synonyms), the Scikit-Learn library is used, specifically the **cosine_similarity** function.

Before calculating this similarity, the user's text undergoes pre-correction with Gemini—for example, "has product X" is automatically adjusted to "has product X." Next, the system performs several checks on the prompt: it searches for similar products or sections, recognizes brands and synonyms, and compares the text embedding with the vectors stored in the database. With this information, the system constructs a new, enriched prompt and finally generates the response for the user.

During the testing phase, the software is verified to ensure it meets the specified requirements. These tests are conducted in an isolated environment, not in production, and simulate different scenarios in which customers and employees interact with the chatbot.

5. Results and Discussion

As a result of this research, Hecate is presented as a web-based system organized into two main areas: a customer service interface and an administrative dashboard for information management.

In the customer area, the interaction begins with a friendly home screen (Figure 13) and then advances to the chatbot dialogue window (Figure 14), where the system greets the user and requests basic identification data.

Figure 13. Customer home screen.

Figure 14. Hecate chatbot dialogue screen.

Thereafter, an initial menu with predefined options is displayed (Figure 15), improving navigation and giving the user faster access to information about products, supermarket services, and other database-linked features.

Figure 15. Screen with the Hecate chatbot's initial options menu.

In the administrative panel, the system includes a welcome screen (Figure 16a), a login screen (Figure 16b), and three user-management functions: new user registration (Figure 16c) and password recovery options (Figures 16d and 16e).

(a)

(b)

(c)

(d)

(e)

Figure 16. Screens of the Hecate administration system: (a) Home; (b) Login; (c) New user registration; (d) and (e) password recovery

Once logged in, the administrator accesses the product registration screen (Figure 17), which contains eight fields: name, brand, quantity/format, section, price, unit of measure, stock quantity, and synonyms. Among these, the name field includes a search function for existing records, helping reduce duplication. In addition, the synonyms field can be filled manually or generated automatically by Gemini, supporting the learning process and expanding the system’s vocabulary.

Figure 17. Administrative system home screen.

The registered products list (Figure 18) allows the administrator to edit or remove items, and any update is reflected in the chatbot’s knowledge base after the learning process. Overall, the Hecate interface was designed to support efficient interaction, continuous knowledge updating, and a structured workflow between customer service and administration.

ID	Produto	Marca	Formato Qt.	Seção	Preço	Ações
56	LEITE EM PO INSTANTANEO	NINHO	36X24	Seção 1	1.70	✎
7	REFRESCO PLUS LARANJA	FRUCTUS	10x12	Seção 3	2.40	✎
55	ALVEJANTE MULTI	BRILLUX	3X1	Seção 1	2.60	✎
59	AGUA SANITARIA	IGUAL	12X24	Seção 3	3.30	✎
60	SABAO LIQ. MULTIACAO DOYP	OMO	46X12	Seção 3	2.50	✎
13	FRALDA DESC. XG CXA	BABY ROGER	1 X 12 18UND	Seção 3	8.40	✎
61	SABAO LIQ. T.ACAO	BRILLUX	26x200G	Seção 1	3.30	✎
6	MILHO VERDE AO VAPOR LATA	FUGINI	36x12	Seção 2	2.00	✎
33	BISC. ROSQ. LEITE	VITAMASSA	10X400G	Seção 2	3.50	✎
62	CERA INCOLOR EMULSIONADA	POLITRIZ	POLIMAX	Seção 2	25.00	✎

Figure 18. Product listing screen.

6. Conclusion

This research presented the development of Hecate, a chatbot designed for customer service in retail establishments, capable of providing more assertive and personalized

responses based on the continuous registration of new products and information. The system enhances customer comfort by providing immediate interaction, replacing static FAQ models with a dynamic virtual assistant.

Among the main challenges were the character limit for free use on Gemini and the need to control prompt length to avoid “hallucinations”—situations in which the AI generates incorrect responses or strays from the context [Hatem, Simmons, and Thornton 2023]. To mitigate this risk, a chain of linked prompts was implemented before Hecate’s final response. Although this approach slightly increases response time, it improves the accuracy and consistency of responses, as the model’s learning process becomes more efficient with each iteration.

Experience has shown that, despite advances in AI, there are practical challenges in applying AI models in real time, which require creative solutions that balance processing robustness and service agility. Full-stack integration, with Python and Django on the backend, React on the frontend, and PostgreSQL for the database, proved viable for building intelligent chatbots. Furthermore, the use of NLP techniques, such as embeddings and lemmatization, deepened the understanding of the user’s context, generating more natural and relevant interactions.

Another relevant point is the adoption of a modular architecture based on the MVC pattern, which clearly separates the presentation and business logic layers. This structure facilitates future maintenance and ensures scalability, allowing Hecate to evolve without compromising system stability.

As future work, we suggest: (i) conducting tests in a real-world environment of establishments to evaluate performance and robustness in production; (ii) implementing retrieval-augmented generation (RAG) to enrich responses with external data [IBM 2023]; (iii) evaluating new libraries and emerging models (e.g., Deepseek) that can improve accuracy and speed; and (iv) making the interface responsive and developing a mobile web application to expand user access.

In summary, Hecate demonstrated the effectiveness of advanced AI techniques in customer service, contributing to digital transformation in the commercial sector and leading to future research aimed at further improving the interaction between humans and intelligent systems.

References

- Abbate, M. L.; Thiel, U.; Kamps, T. Can proactive behavior turn chatterbots into conversational agents? In: *IEEE/WIC/ACM International Conference on Intelligent Agent Technology*, 2005. DOI: 10.1109/IAT.2005.49.
- Adamopoulou, E.; Moussiades, L. Chatbots: history, technology, and applications. *Machine Learning with Applications*, v. 2, p. 100006, 2020. DOI: 10.1016/j.mlwa.2020.100006.
- Adamopoulou, E.; Moussiades, L. An overview of chatbot technology. In: *Artificial Intelligence Applications and Innovations*. 2020. DOI: 10.1007/978-3-030-49186-4_31.

Adamuthe, A. C. Improved text classification using long short-term memory and word embedding technique. *International Journal of Hybrid Information Technology*, v. 13, n. 1, 2020. DOI: 10.21742/IJHIT.2020.13.1.03.

AlGhozali, S.; Mukminatun, S. Natural language processing of Gemini artificial intelligence powered chatbot. *Balankas: An International Multidisciplinary Research Journal*, v. 1, n. 1, p. 41–48, 2024. DOI: 10.66317/688570.

Almeida, F.; Xexéo, G. Word embeddings: a survey. *arXiv preprint*, 2019. Available at: <https://arxiv.org/abs/1901.09069>.

Aslam, F. The benefits and challenges of customization within SaaS cloud solutions. *American Journal of Data, Information and Knowledge Management*, v. 4, n. 1, p. 14–22, 2023. DOI: 10.47672/ajdikm.1543.

Ayanouz, S.; Abdelhakim, B. A.; Benhmed, M. A smart chatbot architecture based NLP and machine learning for health care assistance. In: *International Conference on Networking, Information Systems & Security*, 2020. DOI: 10.1145/3386723.3387897.

Bala, K.; Kumar, M.; Hulawale, S.; Pandita, S. Chat-bot for college management system using A.I. *International Research Journal of Engineering and Technology*, v. 4, n. 4, 2017.

Bitner, M. J.; Brown, S. W.; Meuter, M. L. Technology infusion in service encounters. *Journal of the Academy of Marketing Science*, v. 28, n. 1, p. 138–149, 2000. DOI: 10.1177/0092070300281013.

Cahn, J. *CHATBOT: Architecture, Design, & Development*. 2017. Ph.D. Thesis – University of Pennsylvania.

Camacho-Collados, J.; Pilehvar, M. T. Embeddings in natural language processing. In: *COLING 2020 Tutorials*, p. 10–15, 2020. DOI: 10.18653/v1/2020.coling-tutorials.2.

Carleo, G. et al. Machine learning and the physical sciences. *Reviews of Modern Physics*, v. 91, p. 045002, 2019. DOI: 10.1103/RevModPhys.91.045002.

Cui, L. et al. SuperAgent: a customer service chatbot for e-commerce websites. In: *ACL 2017 System Demonstrations*, p. 97–102, 2017. DOI: 10.18653/v1/P17-4017.

Cunningham, L. F.; Young, C. E.; Gerlach, J. H. Consumer views of self-service technologies. *The Service Industries Journal*, v. 28, n. 6, p. 719–732, 2008. DOI: 10.1080/02642060801988522.

Dewantara, A. S.; Aryanto, J. Implementation of a web-based chatbot using machine learning for question and answer services in universities. *Advance Sustainable Science, Engineering and Technology*, v. 6, n. 1, 2024. DOI: 10.26877/ASSET.V6I1.17590.

Dube, E.; Benedetto, R. E-commerce success. In: *E-Commerce Research Forum*, 2002. Available at: <http://ecommerce.mit.edu/forum/index.html>.

Dwivedi, Y. K. et al. Re-examining the unified theory of acceptance and use of technology (UTAUT). *Information Systems Frontiers*, v. 21, p. 719–734, 2019. DOI: 10.1007/s10796-017-9774-y.

Google. Gemini API documentation. 2024. Available at: <https://ai.google.dev/gemini-api/docs>.

- Google. Gemini API: embeddings. 2024. Available at: <https://ai.google.dev/gemini-api/docs/embeddings>.
- Grewal, D.; Roggeveen, A. L.; Nordfält, J. The future of retailing. *Journal of Retailing*, v. 93, n. 1, p. 1–6, 2017. DOI: 10.1016/j.jretai.2016.12.008.
- Gutiérrez, L.; Keith, B. A. A systematic literature review on word embeddings. In: *Trends and Applications in Software Engineering*. Springer, 2019. DOI: 10.1007/978-3-030-01171-0_12.
- Han, L. et al. UMBC_EBIQUITY-CORE: semantic textual similarity systems. In: *SemEval*, 2013.
- Hastie, T.; Tibshirani, R.; Friedman, J. *The elements of statistical learning*. Springer, 2009.
- Hatem, R.; Simmons, B.; Thornton, J. E. Chatbot confabulations are not hallucinations. *JAMA Internal Medicine*, v. 183, n. 10, p. 1177, 2023. DOI: 10.1001/jamainternmed.2023.4231.
- Huang, P.-S. et al. Learning deep structured semantic models. In: *CIKM*, 2013. DOI: 10.1145/2505515.2505665.
- IBM. Unsupervised learning. 2020. Available at: <https://www.ibm.com/cloud/learn/unsupervised-learning>.
- IBM. What is retrieval-augmented generation? 2023. Available at: <https://research.ibm.com/blog/retrieval-augmented-generation-RAG>.
- Imran, M.; Almusharraf, N. Google Gemini as a next generation AI educational tool. *Smart Learning Environments*, v. 11, n. 1, 2024. DOI: 10.1186/s40561-024-00310-z.
- Jia, J. The study of a keyword-based chatbot system. *arXiv*, 2003.
- Joshi, A. V. *Machine learning and artificial intelligence*. Springer, 2020.
- Kalluri, K.; Kokala, A. Performance benchmarking of generative AI models, 2024.
- Kumar, R.; Ali, M. M. A review on chatbot design and implementation techniques. *International Journal of Engineering and Technology*, 2020.
- Lee, J. et al. Gecko: versatile text embeddings. 2024.
- Loeber, P. Google Gemini. Available at: <https://github.com/google-gemini/generative-ai-python>.
- Mahesh, B. Machine learning algorithms: a review. *International Journal of Scientific Research*, v. 9, 2020.
- Meinshausen, N.; Ridgeway, G. Quantile regression forests. *Journal of Machine Learning Research*, v. 7, 2006.
- Mikolov, T. et al. Efficient estimation of word representations. *arXiv*, 2013.
- Mikolov, T. et al. Distributed representations of words and phrases. In: *NeurIPS*, 2013.
- Min, H. Artificial intelligence in supply chain management. *International Journal of Logistics*, v. 13, n. 1, 2010. DOI: 10.1080/13675560902736537.

- Minaee, S. et al. Image segmentation using deep learning: a survey. *IEEE TPAMI*, v. 44, n. 7, 2022. DOI: 10.1109/TPAMI.2021.3059968.
- Oguntosin, V.; Olomo, A. Development of an e-commerce chatbot. *Applied Computational Intelligence and Soft Computing*, 2021. DOI: 10.1155/2021/6630326.
- Pant, V. K.; Sharma, R.; Kundu, S. Stemming and lemmatization techniques. 2024.
- Pantano, E.; Pizzi, G. Forecasting AI on customer assistance. *Journal of Retailing and Consumer Services*, 2020. DOI: 10.1016/j.jretconser.2020.102096.
- Pennington, J.; Socher, R.; Manning, C. D. GloVe. In: *EMNLP*, 2014. DOI: 10.3115/v1/D14-1162.
- Ren, Z.; Wang, S.; Zhang, Y. Weakly supervised machine learning. *CAAI Transactions*, 2023. DOI: 10.1049/cit2.12216.
- Roy, R.; Naidoo, V. Enhancing chatbot effectiveness. *Journal of Business Research*, 2021. DOI: 10.1016/j.jbusres.2020.12.051.
- Shakya, A. K. et al. Reinforcement learning algorithms. *Expert Systems with Applications*, 2023. DOI: 10.1016/j.eswa.2023.120495.
- Sharifani, K. and Amini, M. (2023). Machine learning and deep learning: A review of methods and applications. In: *World Information Technology and Engineering Journal*, v. 10, n. 07.
- Sojasingarayar, A. (2020). Seq2Seq AI Chatbot with Attention Mechanism. Master's Thesis, IA School/University-GEMA Group.
- Srivastava, A. (2021). The Application & Impact of Artificial Intelligence (AI) on E-Commerce.
- Stickdorn, M.; Schneider, J. *Isto é design thinking de serviços*. Porto Alegre: Bookman, 2014.
- Team, G. et al. Gemini: a family of highly capable multimodal models. *arXiv*, 2023.
- Wilson, H. J.; Daugherty, P. R.; Morini-Bianzino, N. The jobs that AI will create. 2018. DOI: 10.7551/mitpress/11645.003.0020.
- Worth, P. J. Word embeddings and semantic spaces. *International Journal of Intelligence Science*, 2023. DOI: 10.4236/ijis.2023.131001.
- Zafar, M. Developing smart conversation agent ECOM-BOT. *International Journal of Information Engineering and Electronic Business*, 2023. DOI: 10.5815/ijieeb.2023.02.01.